

**THE SOCIO-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF NAMES IN NIGERIAN LANGUAGES A STUDY OF
SOME GEOPOLITICAL ZONES IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study examines variety of names of persons and places from three geopolitical zones in Nigeria to determine the social functions of those names and what the names mean in the context in which they are used. The main objective of the investigation is to have a broad understanding of the socio-cultural and semantic value of names ascribed to people and places in the three geopolitical zones, North Central, South-West, and South-South Zones respectively. The descriptivist theory propounded by Russell and Frege (1980) and Chalmers (2005) was used to guide the study. Seven names of persons and three names of places are selected from each of the zones and analyzed. The analysis shows that names given to people and places vary and are significant in the context in which they are used. It is recommended that people in the different locations in Nigeria should not only be encouraged to bear names that help to identify them but also to consider the extended meanings of such names.

Key words: socio semantic, analysis, Nigerian languages, geopolitics

Introduction

Anthropologists have argued about the relationship between the term 'system' and another term 'person' or 'individual' as the case may be. System, according to them can refer to various concepts, such as culture, society, social relations and social structure. Individual human being, it is assumed, always make up or constitute the system. Living within the system human beings are constrained to some extent, at least, by its rule and by the actions of other individuals. People learn, interpret and

manipulate the same rule in different ways to suit their interests.

Culture is greatly contested, different groups in society struggle with one another over whose ideas, values, goals and beliefs prevail. Common symptom may have entirely different meaning to different individual and groups in the same culture. This contention is constant in cultural environments where people or group of people reside. Even when they agree about what should and should not be done, people do not always do as their culture permits

or as other people expect. Culture is both public and individual, both in the world and in peoples' mind, that is, how individuals think, feel and behave. Cultural learning entails that people create, remember, and deal with ideas. One is expected to grasp and apply specific systems of symbolic meaning. This explains why Anthropologist, Clifford Geertz defines culture as ideas based on cultural learning and symbols. According to Geertz (1973) cultures have been characterized as sets of control mechanisms, plans, recipes, rules, instructions, what computer engineers call programs for the regulation of behavior.

These programs are absorbed by people through enculturation in particular traditions. People gradually internalize a previously established system of meaning and symbol. They, then, use this cultural system to define their world, express their feelings, and make their judgments. This system, it is believed, guide their behavior and perceptions throughout their lives. Consequently, the people pay attention, to and recognize as well as celebrate significant aspect of their culture which includes, child naming ceremony, mode of greeting, storytelling, art and craft, dances, songs, cultural festival, marriage rites and burial rites among others. Language is at the centre of all that have been cited, for it is generally believed that language expresses culture. It is the significant tool or instrument we use to express or talk about culture. In fact, language can be used to express whatever we want to express. According to Essien (1977) language is not only used to express positive things and values, but it is also used to inform, explain, direct, enlighten, praise, sing, pray, teach and even used to cheat, lie, misinform and insult.

Language is used to facilitate communication among human beings in the society. More importantly, language is used to express one's identity. It is in this regard that this paper would be tailored. This paper examines variety of names of persons and places from three geo-political zones in Nigeria. Our main objective in this paper is to investigate the social functions of names in Nigerian languages and what the names mean in the context in which they are used. It is also to enable us have a broad understanding of the socio-cultural, and semantic value of all such names ascribed to people and places in the three geo-political zones, North central, South West and South-South zones respectively. Seven names of persons and three names of places are selected from each of the zones.

Our data is obtained from Benue State in the North Central zone, Ogun State in the South West zone, and Cross River and AkwaIbom States in South-South Zone.

In North Central, the focus is on the Idoma speaking people, in South West, the Yoruba speaking people and in South-South, the Efik and Ibibio speaking people. For clarity of purpose, attempt is made to comment briefly on the history of Idoma and the Idoma cosmology, (ie Idoma world view) from where these names derive.

History of Idoma

The Idoma people of the Federal Republic of Nigeria trace their origin of decent from a common ancestor 'Idu'¹ whose descendants speak 'Kwa' language and who were said to have migrated from the East to a location called, Apa as their ancestral homeland, a place located by historians as a territory of the ancient kwararafa Empire which dominated the Gongola/Upper Benue Basin at about the close of the 13th Century and the late 14th Century.

The empire started to disintegrate as a result of socio-economic and political upheavals which led many groups with historical affinity with the Idoma race to migrate to different directions at different times thus, making the Idomas migrate to their present location. Such other brother groups involved in the migration included the Igbira and the Igalas of the present Kogi State, the Alagos (a.k.a. IdomaNokwu) of Nasarawa State, the Yalas and Ogojas of Cross River State, the Ettes of Igbo-Eze in Enugu State, the Etulos of Benue State and the Jukuns of Taraba State. The Idomas as oral history has it are said to have a common ancestor known as 'Idu' from whom the name 'Ai-Iduma' (ie the children begotten by Idu) was coined and later anglicized 'Idoma'. They speak at least four mutually intelligible dialects, namely, Igede, Ufia, Akweya and Agatu in addition to the central Idoma popularly known as 'Akpoto'.

However, another source has it that at the migratory period of the 16th Century, the leader of the emigrants who were mostly proto-Idoma groups was called, 'Idu' the son of Oma (ie IduO'Oma), which was later anglicized 'Idoma'¹. In spite of this historical variations, suffice it to say that between the 10th and 18th centuries according to Professor E. O. Erim, the Idoma proto-groups through a process of outward and inward migration, consolidated their geo-political boundaries

and settled in their present location thus, currently sharing boundaries with Nasarawa State to the North; Kogi State to the West; Enugu and Ebonyi States to the South and Cross River State, Gwer and Gwer West Local Government of Benue State to the East. Though found in pockets of settlements in Nasarawa, Kogi and Cross River States, the Idomas inhabit the present geographical entity known as Idomaland. It presently comprises of nine local Government Areas namely, Ado, Agatu, Apa, Obi, Ogbadibo, Ohimini, Okpokwu, Oju and Otukpo. Presently, Otukpo is the traditional headquarters of Idoma people. The Idoma people speak the Idoma language, which is their indigenous language.

The Idoma Cosmology

It is within the spectacle of the Alekwu festival celebration that the belief system of what is usually referred to as the World view of the Idoma people unfolds.

The following are essential indications:

- The belief in the existence of a god-called, 'Owoicho'
- The fact that Owoicho came down from heaven
- Owoicho is the creator of heaven and earth
- Controls the activities of every man, woman, old, and young people including the living and the dead
- Owoicho is the controller of the environment (i.e. land, this is known as 'Aje' by the Idoma people and for this purpose, the elders of Idoma appease the 'gods' by celebrating the 'Aje Day' which they call, (Eje-Aje).
- The alekwu festival to the Idoma people, is a recognition of the enormous contributions and care of the 'Owoicho -manchalla' (i.e. Almighty God) towards their wellbeing and peaceful co-existence as a people.
- Essentially, the festival is celebrated to thank God for protecting them as a people and giving them good harvest, season and granting them peace of mind, soul and body throughout the year.

Here, lies the significance of the event. Masquerading is an important feature in the Alekwu Festival celebration, kolanut, palm wine, goat and gruel, yams and pounded yams form part of the celebration.

Theoretical Consideration

The theory we have considered for this study is the Descriptivist theory. This theory which is also called, the descriptivist theory of proper names and atimes referred to as descriptivist theory of reference, holds the view that the meaning or semantic content of a proper name is identical to the descriptions that are associated with it by the speakers, while their referents are determined to be the objects that satisfy these descriptions.

Associated with this theory of name are Bertrand Russell and Gottlob Frege. For this reason, the theory is sometimes referred to as the 'Frege – Russell view'. Critics of the theory are of the opinion that the theory is not adequate enough to account for the numerous functions performed by proper names and that the meaning emanating from this theory about names are limited in scope. Prominent among the critics of this theory are Saul Kripke and Hilary Putnam.

David Chalmers in later periods attempted a modification of the theory and called it, 'the two - dimensional semantic theories'. In a more scientific way, according to Chalmers, for every proper name P, there is some collection of descriptions D, that are associated with P, and which constitute the meaning of P. As he puts it; the proper name, 'Saul Kripke' can be described as follows:

1. The man who wrote 'Naming and Necessity'.
2. A person who was born on November 13, 1940 in Bay shore, New York, and so on.
3. Based on this vivid explanation, the descriptivist theory by Chalmers, two important points about the theory are obvious: 1. is that the meaning of a given proper name is made up of collection or series of descriptions and that the referent(s) (i.e those phenomena or things) which the name is linked with automatically become the conditions or characteristics that satisfy all or most of the descriptions.

What this means is that no name that is assigned or given is said to be autonomous or referred to in isolation. Hence, every proper name of a person or place does not only identify the person or place but also describes the person or place in a variety of ways and circumstances.

Presentation of data (North Central Zone)**Table 1: Seven personal names in North Central Geo-political zone**

	Name	Type	Language	Circumstance	Connotation	Meaning
1	Oriko-oko	Personal	Idoma	Ancestral	Ancestral descent	Oriko- Oko the daughter of Oko
2	Ogiri-Oko	Personal	Idoma	Ancestral	Ancestral link	Ogiri-oko, the son of Oko
3	Onyewu	Personal	Idoma	Historical/Heroism/ Time	A product of war	A woman of war, given to war, characterized by war etc
4	Olotu	Personal	Idoma	Historical/Heroism	Bravery	Warrior, defender, champion etc
5	Emaikwu	Personal	Idoma	Death/Time	Deprivation/appeal	Born to die, susceptible to death, born to live and not to die again
6	Onyemowo	Personal	Idoma	Destiny/philosophy	Unpredictability/mystical	Beyond human understanding, no one can say, predict or understand the unknown the hidden treasure, time alone shall tell.
7	Ogbole	Personal	Idoma	Quest for a male child/desire for a male child	Home guard	He who takes care of the home. Home keeper and the watchman or person of the house
8	Ojira	Place (a suburb)	Idoma	Social gathering	Convergence/ togetherness	Meeting, meeting place/centre, place or arena where people meet
9	Orokam	Place (a village/district)	Idoma	Historical/adventure	Okam place/home	The place Okam lives, Okam's home or settlement
10	Ododo-Aje	Place (a village)	Idoma	Historical/geographical/adventure	Sunset/time	The particular place or direction where the sun sets before night fall

South-West Zone

Table 2: Seven personal names and three place names in the South-West geopolitical zone

	Name	Type	Language	Circumstance	Connotation	Meaning
1	Oshokoya	Personal	Yoruba	Difficulty/hard time	God forbid	No more problem, it is all over, suffering has ceased
2	Moyebi	Personal	Yoruba	Protracted illness/long suffering	Survival	An overcomer, the redeemed
3	Omomuyiwa	Personal	Yoruba	Miraculous	Surprise/ welcome, God’s time	We have been finally remembered. The expected male child has come, God has answered our prayers
4	Yetunde	Personal	Yoruba	Heritary/birth/death	Reincarnation	Substitute, in place of, replacement.
5	Oluwafumilayo	Personal	Yoruba	Childlessness	Joyous visitation/ Blessing	Happiness, joy, fulfillment, accomplishment, God’s has given me joy
6	Ilesami	Personal	Yoruba	Appreciation/praise	Favour, goodness	My home favours me, Peace of mind, harmonious, home devoid of rancour
7	Adebowale	Personal	Yoruba	Coronation	Coin incidence	The crown has returned home
8	Abeokuta	Place (city)	Yoruba	Historical/belief/ mythology	Protection/Refuge	Shelter, shield, refugee camp, safety, security.
9	Osun	Place (city)	Yoruba	ill health, uncleanliness disease/sickness	Healing/care	A place of restoration, revival and wellness.
10	Ogun	Place (city)	Yoruba	Ancestral/historical/ religious	Deity	God of iron in charge of people, morality, judgment and protection. It ensures discipline, order and good governance.

Analysis of Data

Table 1: Data from North Central Zone

The data is a list of personal names and names of places in Idoma. Among the Idoma people in the different communities where they live, importance is attached to naming. Children are assigned names the moment they are born or given birth to. Like most societies in Africa, Idoma names are given according to the system of naming and in relation to the tradition and culture of the people. The assignment of these names is an exclusive preserve of the parents of the child, all of which derive from the value system of the Idoma people. The practice however varies from community to community. While some mark naming ceremonies on low key, others celebrate it elaborately to express their joy and gratitude to God for blessing them with a new baby.

On such occasions, family members, friends, well-wishers, youths and elderly members of the community are invited to witness and participate in this important socio-cultural and communal event. This is hinged on the belief that one is the other person’s brother or sister and on an occasion like that, they need to come together to express joy to God, share things in common and thank God for greater blessings ahead.

Among the Idoma people, especially, the parents of the child, before names are assigned consideration will be given to the circumstance of birth from the point of view of the parent, child, the ancestors, friends of the family, philosophy, historical events, predestination and incidences of sickness and death.

The names provided in table 1 are all typical examples of names that are associated with aspects of the socio-cultural economic, political and religious practices of the Idoma people.

The first and second name in table 1, 'Ogiri-Oko' and 'Oriko-Oko', for instance are names that link parents of the children to their fore fathers, while 'Ogiri-Oko' is a name given in honour and in remembrance of the grandfather of the new born child, Oriko-Oko is assigned to link the female born child to her patrilineal home. Hence, we have 'Ogiri-Oko', the grandson of 'Oko' and Oriko-Oko, the grant daughter of Oko. The looks or appearance of the new born is a strong factor that could spur the parents to decide to name the children after his own fore father or ancestor. Item (3 in table 1 is historical, time bound and Heroic.) The possible interpretation of this name could be: a female born in war time, a female defender of the oppressed, who has come at the outbreak of war, or as earlier indicated in table 1, 'a woman of war' 'one given to war' or 'one whose birth is characterized by war', because she was born at the time of war. This is so because the Idoma word for war is 'Ewu'. 'Kpewu', is the Idoma word for 'fight a war'. Similar explanation goes for the next name in table 1, item no. 4. 'Olotu.' The name suggests one who is tough, strong, fearless, bold and one who can stand or face anybody, or situation, who dares to challenge or confront him; in short, the name by extension, means; 'the insurmountable'.

The name 'Emaikwu,' item (5) on the table is another name in Idoma that is very significant. It is a name that relates to death and time. If a family frequently experiences death of its newborn each time, a child is delivered, such a family is gripped by fear in that, the members of the family would always think that once,, any other child is born, the child is bound to die like the ones before it. Ironically, this is not always so because the parents in their disillusioned state would resort to invocation and a strong appeal to the Supreme Being to spare the next child that will be born to the family. To achieve this, in their prayers, they will remind God that they have never been favoured at the birth of any child, because their own history and fate is to loose the child each time it was born which is the real meaning of the name. 'Emaikwu' means, 'death! do not strike again this time! Spare us this one, please. Such an appeal may or may not work, depending on the personal relationship of the parents to their God. It is important to state that the

majority of the data (i.e names) cited in table 1 are names used to identify children born in Western Idoma.

The three (3) place names or names of places in table 1 are also significant because they are names derived from the tradition and culture of the Idoma people. Above all, each of the names has meaning, both socially and semantically. Ojira, is a name of a suburb in Otukpo town, the headquarters of Idomaland. It is, to the people, 'a new settlement', 'a developing part of Otukpo', that is likely to give the town, a facelift, with time.

'Orokam is the actual name of the village of one of the researchers in this study. It is in Ogbadibo local government area of Benue State. The name means; the abode of 'Okam'. Okam was said to be the first person to settle in the jungle, now called, 'Orokam,' which actually means, 'Ole-Okam' i.e the home of the first settler, 'Okam.' 'Ododo-Aje' is in Otukpo and it signifies, the place/land where there is 'Ododo' that colour from the sky that usually cover the surrounding when the sun sets. This phenomenon not only signals time but heralds nightfall in Idoma.

Analysis of data

Table 2: Data from South West zone

The Yoruba speaking people of south western Nigeria are people with rich and amiable culture with diverse form of artistic and aesthetic values that are held in high esteem. Like every other society or community in Africa, they have their system of naming, whether such names are names of persons or names of things or places.

A careful study of the names cited in table 2 of this study will show that the names have been carefully selected to reflect the situation which gave rise to them. This is because the Yoruba belief system accord respect to names because of the values/traditions which those names represent. The gods occupy important position in the explanation of events in the life of the average Yoruba person and such influence of the role of the ancestors or ancestral gods and goddesses are epitomized in the names given to the children by their parents.

According to the information derived from a native speaker of the language, Yoruba names are significant names because they are in most cases, a reflection of the socio-cultural, economic, religious and political lives of the people. It is in this regard that attempt is made to give a detailed explanation of the social function and semantic

implications of personal names and names of cities in Yoruba.

According to the informant, the name ‘oshokoya’, is given to the child at birth, particularly during the child’s ‘naming ceremony’, which is usually very elaborate. If before the child was born, the parents were encountering a great deal of problem or difficulties, the arrival of the new born is an indication that the prevailing difficult situation will end with the birth of the child. Consequently, the name ‘Oshokoya’, which means, ‘the gods reject suffering,’ would be given to the child.

The second name, item (2) in the table, ‘Moyebi’ is assigned to a child whose parents never believe that the unborn child would survive in the mother’s womb because of protracted illness which both parents suffered during the child’s pregnancy. To the parents, it was a case of ‘we do not think that the child’ will make it, that is , develop very well in the mother’s womb and be delivered. Hence, the name ‘Moyebi’ meaning ‘thank the gods for sparing the child for us.’ Oh! Thank God, she survived. Credit and gratitude in this regard is given to the gods who are known to be the source of their livelihood, protection and care in all ramification.

The name ‘Omomuyiwa,’ item (3) in the table, is also significant. It is so because, according to the informant, such a name is usually given to the child whose parents have lost hope of having a male child, particularly when the parents had been expecting to have a male child for a very long time after they had been married. The name in this regard, means ‘gratitude to God for his goodness and mercy to the parents and other members of the family. To them, it was a dream, a miracle, a surprise and above all, God’s time which is always the best, for they have been patient and waited for this. Even though, they least expect, it has come.’

‘Yetunde’ item (4) in the table connotes a rebirth, reincarnation, particularly when a female child is born whose features is assumed to be a complete feature of her mother, who dies immediately the child is delivered. Even when the personal qualities of the child do not in any way relate to that of their late mother, the child would still be given the name, in memory of the late mother. The male equivalence of ‘Yetunde’ is ‘Babatunde’ which means, ‘father is back’, in a different form as one can see from

the resemblance between the newly born baby boy and his late father.

The meaning adduced to item No. 5 in the table is almost the same with the explanation offered in respect of item 3. Omomuyiwa. The only difference is that the parents of the former were already bearing children, but had only female ones, while in the latter case, the parents were childless completely before the child finally came.

As we can see from item 5.in the table, ‘Oluwafumilayo’, signifies ‘joy’ happiness’, fulfillment.

Place names or names of places

As indicated in the table, three names which mean so much to the Yoruba people have been cited, ‘Abeokuta’, ‘Osun’, and ‘Ogun’. The three names have both spiritual and religious undertone. Element of history, legend, folk-tale and philosophy are also associated with the names. At a glance, one will notice that the names serve a dual function; ‘old meaning’ and ‘new meaning’. Each of the names refer to a specific ‘god’ in the world view of the Yorubas, the god of stone, god of healing/cure and god of iron, with each god personified as having the potential to exert some influence on the offsprings of the Yoruba ancestors.’

Today, these old terms have assumed a new role of being names of state capitals in the Old Oyo-Empire. Abeokuta, the Capital of OndoState, Osun, Capital of OsunState and Ogun, Capital of OgunState. The meaning and relevance attached to the place names in the South West Zone are entirely different from the ones we saw or head about in North Central Zone.

South South zone

The South South geopolitical zone of Nigeria is located within the southern most tip of Nigeria where naming constitute a significant phenomenon. Names are chosen to convey a certain meaning, they are not haphazardly chosen. For the purpose of this paper, it is necessary to note that the South-South geopolitical zone is vast and highly multilingual, some of the speech forms are non-native. We in this paper, concentrate on the speech forms that are indigenous or native to the area which we recognize and present based on the standing classification of Niger-Congo working group. We mention the linguistic groups spoken as mother tongues in Akwa Ibom, and Cross River States as follows;

- ◆ Bantoid (Etung)

- ◆ Ibibiod (Efik, Ibibio, Anaang
- ◆ Idomoid (Yala)
- ◆ Bendi (Bokyi)

These linguistic groups share relationship significantly at the level of the new Benue-Congo. This aspect of the research concerns itself with the socio-cultural family positional names especially, the first three males and females of the family.

Among the group of languages spoken in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States within the South-South geopolitical zone, it would appear that only the Ibibiod allocate special cultural family positional names. The other linguistic groups have a more global attitude although the first son and the first Daughters still occupy pride of place in the family. These other groups merely describe the position occupied by each person. We will see some of these allocation in the various linguistic groups Bantoid group (information taken from Etung dialect).

Ekoid Bantoid is represented in the Cross River State by Ejagham clusters of dialects spoken from Calabar town by the Quas, Eakins, Kasuk peoples in Biqua Akim, Ediba Nyagazan, Akaya etc. Others are in Oban, Ikom, extending to the Cameroons. Information about culturally allocated family names include;

- | | | |
|---------------|---|---------------------------|
| Oromaifuneto | - | Etung 1 st son |
| Gwanaaifuneto | - | 1 st daughter |
| Funaba | - | Twins |

Adiaha: A jealous position, highly regarded, the husband occupies a special place Ebe Adiaha- Adiaha husband.

Unwa: 2nd daughter is common to the women’s family affairs
 2nd daughter equivalent of Udo
 2nd race of Adiaha and her strong supporter/ representative when applicable education or wealth cannot enhance or usurp family position, rather, it helps Adiaha to consolidate and perform better.

Unwan –Uwan: 3rd daughter
 No specific roles
 Allocation of duty & inheritance vary from family to family.

Udonwan: 4th daughter
 No specific role

Last Born: Ukpikke eyin
 Asana edem enyin
 Baby of the family

pampered even in adulthood of most respected older siblings.

Ibibio constitutes a vast linguistic area. For the purposes of this study, we want to limit our scope to the three language clusters within Ibibioid, namely, Ibibio, Efik, Aaang, examples of names discussed, and analyzed are drawn mainly from these three languages but mention has been made of a few other languages outside the cluster and Ibibioid. Our focus is on family positional names, Ibibioid the categories and positions children occupy. Each position must be protected and guarded jealously.

Akpan: Leadership/ authority birthrite, not contestable custody of the heritage because he takes responsibility for arrests and liabilities. He is also responsible for redeeming family inheritance, continuity of family, enjoys double portion of the family inheritance, and acts as the principal representative of the family.

Udo: [Udo] second in command can perform delegated duties just in case of vacuum, inherits 2nd portion position next of kin.

Elak udo: 3rd position male 3rd in command.

Udofia: At shaping of family inheritance 3rd portion. Wealth does not change birth rite.

Adiaha: The nurtured, respected one leader of the female members of the family represents the mother, special rites and privileges accrue to her by custom and tradition. A well recognized person- not to be joked with, member of standing family committees opinion leader, especially in women affairs.

Lower Cross

Ibibio (land)

1st born male - Akpan

1st born female – Adiaha

2nd born male - Udo

2nd born female -Ufiwa/nnwa

3rd born male – Etok udo/Ufia

3rd born female – unwa- unwa

4th born male – udo-udo/udofia

4th born female –udonwaan

5th born male

5th born female

Last born male Asana edem

5th born female – Asana edem

Efik (1st)

1st born male - Akpan

1st born female – Adiaha

2nd born male - Udo

2nd born female

3rd born male

3rd born female

4th born male

4th born female

5th born male

5th born female

Last born male

5th born female

Annang (3rd)

1st born male

1st born female

2nd born male

2nd born female

3rd born male

3rd born female

4th born male

4th born female

5th born male

5th born female

Last born male

5th born female

As the name implies, upper cron languages are found in the morthur Cross River State of Nigeria. Some of the major members are Mbembe, Yakurr, Kohumou and the familial potential names identifies in call

of the above groups are;

1. **Undu Bontoild**

1st born (male)

1st born (female)

2nd born (male)

2nd born (female)

3rd born (male)

3rd born (female)

Last born (male)	Okpa anyinchien	-	3 rd son
Last born (female)	Nkuligekuwan	-	4 th son
3 rd born (male)	Okpaonyinyia	-	1 st daughter
3 rd born (female)	Nkuliekuanyinnyin	-	2 nd daughter
4 th born (male)	Ndiesim nwan	-	last daughter
4 th born (female)			
5 th born (male)			
5 th born (female)			
Anaang Abak	Idoma language		
Akpan 1 st son	1 st son – Okpra		1 st daughter – ‘Ada’
Udo 2 nd son	2 nd son- Omacho ompa		2 nd daughter
Udo-Udo 3 rd son	3 rd son - omacho ometa		3 rd daughter
Udoiyo – Udoiyo	4 th son omacho omene		4 th daughter
Udofia	5 th son omacho omelo		5 th daughter
Bendi group	Last son oyi-anome (onyiro)		last daughter
Bokyi	Last child – oyiamome		
Mbobgo shuwan	-	1 st son	
Nyin iewan	-	2 nd son	

Place names

A research in place names is justified by the fact that they tend to remain associated with particular places and events as observed by McIntosh (1952: 23) place names are less liable to change and they constitute to a large extent the base vocabulary, so inevitably, they custody true social and the sociolinguistic/semantic properties and characteristics of the languages, the speakers and other societies (Akpan 2013: 105). Example includes;

1. Mbiakpan
Spies or 1st son
Source land Group

Mbia translates as spies or surveillance group, for Akpan the first son and leader in intertribal and

interethnic wars, manages the socio-cultural surveillance groups. Even after these wars, those members of the group established

themselves in place that has become permanent until date.

Mbia kpaan

Spies’ personal name, translated as the one available- available to lead, available to protect, available to fight, available to sacrifice etc.

2. Ndoon Utim estate of welders or iron workers, Estate, welding - a reflector. Place whose welders were found in a group, or a family of welders.
3. Ekpene Ukpa -Familiar of the read

- ironwood
4. Ikot edem odo - edem odo's people

People 1st name surname Ikpono (Ikp) translated as one and only one, isolated, no brother, no close

Summary/conclusion

This paper investigated into the socio-cultural and semantic aspects of selected names of Nigerian languages in three geo-political zones namely, North Central, South West and South-South geo-political zones.

In each zone, relevant data in the area of indigenous names of persons and places were elicited and analyzed and the result shows that Nigerian languages have rich cultural heritage, particularly in the area of indigenous Nigerian names of persons and place. The study revealed

relative. It denotes the condition of the bearer as lacking relatives, and so deserves to be considered, pitied, helped and encouraged by the society etc.

that not only are the names significant socio-culturally but are also relevant in terms of the meanings which they convey.

The study has also highlighted the significant role first born male and female play within the family unit. A great deal of expectation is required of the first born male within the family hierarchy.

Though a lot of enquiry can still be made about the geopolitical zones that have not been captured in this study, this study has given us a fair idea of what obtains in the geopolitical zones investigated.

References

- Aba, E. O. (2008): Understanding Idoma Folktales, A recounting of Two Tales, in Idoma In Perspective, Nol.
- Agbo, N. O. A. Short history of Idoma Lagos, freedom Books.
- Akpan and Akpan (2013): Place names in post colonial Africa: A case study of Ibibio languages. *Asian journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*.
- Chalmers, David. (2005) Two – Dimensional Semantics. In E. Leopore and B. Smith, eds. The Oxford Handbook of philosophy of language. Oxford University Press.
- Connel B. (1994): the lower Cross languages a prolegomena to the classification of Cross River Language, *Journal of West African Language*.
- Essien O. E. (1990): A Grammar of the Ibibio Language Ibadan University Press Limited.
- Essien, E. O. (1977): The role of English language and development, in Akpan M.D (ed) African development studies Vol. 1. Vol. 1
- Essien, O. E. (1986) Ibibio Names Their Structure and meaning, Ibadan. Day Star Press.
- Faradan, N. (1989) Cross River, J. T. Bendor seminal (ed) The Niger Congo languages Lanham. University of America press.
- Greenberg, J. (1963): The Languages of Africa United states of America. The Hague: Mouton & Co.
- Greetz, C. (1973) The Interpretation of Cultures. New York Basic Books.
- Kripke, Saul (1980) Naming and Necessity. Boston. Basil Blackwell.
- Mcintosh, A. (1952): Introduction to a survey of Scottish Dialects. Edinburgh. Thomas Nelson and sons Limited.
- Onu, O. O. (2016): History and Origin of Ishilor-Orokam. Lagos Ivory Discovery House Media.
- Ukpong, E. A. (2007): An enquiry into culture; Ibibio Names. Uyo Dorand Publishers (2012).
- Williamson, Kay, (1989) Niger Congo, overview J. T. Bendor Samuel (ed). The Niger Congo Languages Lanham University of America Press.